

**Selected Papers from SBLP 2007: The 11th Brazilian
Symposium on Programming Languages
J.UCS Special Issue**

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This special issue comprises a selection of the papers presented at XI Brazilian Symposium on Programming Languages, SBLP 2007, which took place in the city of Natal, Rio Grande do Norte, Brazil, from May, 23 to May, 25, 2007.

SBLP is a series of annual conferences promoted by the Brazilian Computer Science Society. SBLP 2007, which was organized by the Computer Science Department (DIMAp) of the Federal University of Rio Grande do Norte (UFRN), in Natal, featured: (i) **two invited talks**: *Modularity, Information Hiding, and Interfaces for Aspect-Oriented Languages* (Paulo Borba, Universidade Federal de Pernambuco, Brazil) and *CDuce, an XML Processing Programming Language from Theory to Practice* (Giuseppe Castagna, CNRS, Universit Paris 7, France) (ii) **two tutorials** and (iii) the oral presentation of **15 research papers**.

The Program Committee has selected the 15 technical papers from a total of 45 full paper submissions. Submitted papers came from Brazil, Germany, Portugal, France and India. Papers submission deadline was January 19, 2007, and the acceptance date March 22, 2007.

We would like to thank everyone, particularly the Program Committee, who contributed to the evaluation and selection of the papers for the special issue on Programming Languages.

Roberto S. Bigonha
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